

Preferred Method of Teaching Learning and Its Reasons: A Descriptive Study among Medical Students

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Abstract:

Background: Education is a dynamic process, teaching and learning has remarkably progressed. Implementation of New CBME curriculum introduced various innovative methods of teaching which not only improves the knowledge and technical skills but also increases the analytical and communication skills, interests towards the learning.

Objectives: (1). To determine the most preferred method of teaching learning method among medical students (2). To know the various reasons for choosing the teaching learning method among medical students.

Materials and method: The study was conducted among 143 students studying in first MBBS. The students were asked to fill the form containing pre-designed questionnaire and were informed about the purpose of the study.

Results: Among all different teaching learning methods, 34.25% students preferred teaching by power point presentation (PPT) over other methods. Most of the students mentioned that CBL classes are needed for better understanding, higher thinking of students and analytical approach for the topic.

Conclusion: The study concludes that, the most preferred method of teaching were PPT and CBL in comparison to other methods. Students also chose other methods of teaching for better understanding, higher order thinking and easy way of learning.

Keywords: Teaching Learning Method, Medical Students, Reasons, Seminars.

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Introduction

The implementation of competency based medical education (CBME) curriculum for medical students is mainly designed to train the Indian Medical Graduates (IMG) to acquire ethics, knowledge, skills, values and communication to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the teaching learning.

Therefore, CBME has introduced various methods of teaching like case based learning (CBL), integrated teaching, early clinical exposure (ECE), small group discussion (SGD), seminars, etc over traditional formal classroom teaching which is student centered, outcome-based approach to improve the various skills. [1] The effectiveness of the teaching learning can be assessed by assessing the students learning. [2] Every method of teaching has its own merits and demerits. However, successful

teaching learning requires more attractive way of teaching with active participation of teachers and students. [3] Learning is an active process, it requires active involvement of both teachers as well as students to make the process easier and enjoyable. [4] Well organized lecture with efficient use of newer technologies in the form of audio visual aids like power point presentation has become the more powerful mode of teaching. [5]

In traditional way of teaching, it is very difficult to deliver the content effectively and also to retain the attention of students is a very big task. [6] So, implementation of newer methods like PPT, CBL, integrated teaching, SGD, ECE, demonstrations, seminars, etc demands the active participation of the students which improves the easy understanding, higher order thinking, confidence, better ana-

lytical approach towards the subject. [7] The purpose of the study is to know the effectiveness of different methods of teaching among students.

Objective:

1. To determine the most preferred method of teaching learning method among medical students
2. To know the various reasons for choosing the teaching learning method among medical students

Materials and methodology:

The present study was conducted among 150 students of first MBBS of batch 2023-24 studying at Chikkamagaluru institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru during the month of April 2024. out of which 143 students questionnaire was completely filled which was considered for the final

analysis. Institutional ethical committee approval was taken before conducting the survey. They were in the age group of 18-20 years. None of them suffering from any major psychiatric or medical illness. The students were asked to fill the survey containing pre-designed questionnaire on different teaching learning methods like PPT, chalk and talk, seminars, CBL, integrated teaching, ECE, demonstration, SGD, etc. The students were informed about the purpose of the study and consent was taken.

Statistical analysis: Data was be entered in the excel spread sheet. Descriptive statistics of the variables was calculated by frequency and proportion for qualitative variables.

Data was represented graphically wherever necessary using pie diagram.

Results:

Graph 1: Teaching learning methods preferred among medical students

Table 1: Reasons for choosing the Teaching Learning method among students

Reason for choosing the method	Chalk and talk	PPT	Seminar	SGD	CBL	ECE	Integrated teaching	Demonstration
Better Understanding	33(23.06%)	20(13.98%)	2(1.39%)	13(9.08%)	36(25.16%)	5(3.49%)	20(13.98%)	14(9.78%)
Better Thinking	6(4.19%)	6(4.19%)	5(3.49%)	22(15.37%)	59(41.24%)	9(6.29%)	25(17.47%)	11(7.68%)
Better Concept	18(12.58%)	29(20.27%)	2(1.39%)	9(6.29%)	29(20.27%)	12(8.38%)	32(22.36%)	12(8.38%)
Increase Motivation	9(6.29%)	8(5.59%)	17(11.88%)	18(12.58%)	31(21.66%)	26(18.17%)	22(15.37%)	12(8.38%)
Improve Analytical Approach	15(10.48%)	11(7.68%)	8(5.59%)	25(17.47%)	37(25.86%)	21(14.67%)	15(10.48%)	10(6.99%)
Improves the Confidence	13(9.08%)	7(4.89%)	54(37.74%)	16(11.18%)	21(14.67%)	12(8.38%)	14(9.78%)	6(4.19%)
More Interactive	23(16.07%)	6(4.19%)	12(8.38%)	50(34.95%)	23(16.07%)	11(7.68%)	14(9.78%)	4(2.79%)

Graph 1 & Table 1: Shows the students preferences about different teaching and learning

methods. 34.25% students preferred teaching by power point presentation (PPT) is the most pre-

ferred method of teaching followed by teaching by chalk and talk (31.45%) over other methods. 25.16%, 41.24% and 25.86% students mentioned CBL classes are needed for better understanding, higher order thinking of students and analytical approach for the topic respectively. 22.36% students opined that they get better concept by integrated teaching. 37.74% students expressed seminars improved the confidence of the students towards topic. 34.95% students stated that small group discussion is the best interactive method of teaching.

Discussion:

The results of the present study shows that power point teaching is the most preferred way of teaching by using audio visual aids which helps in better understanding of the topic.

Studies done by Rajani SN, Yogananda R, Rajesh P, et al shows that students have preference for chalk and talk with PPT. [8] Majority of the students in our group opined that more case based learning classes are needed for better understanding, for higher order of thinking and analysis of the topic.

Our findings are similar to the study conducted by Vimal MH et al [7], Carpenter J et al [9] states that teaching along with discussion as in CBL helps the students to be active learners, engaging in discussion rather than passive listener.

Our results on small group discussion as the best interactive way of teaching were in consistent with findings of the study by Vijaya SD et al. [10] on effect of integrated teaching versus conventional lecturing on MBBS phase I Students states that small group discussion is efficient way of teaching as it motivates active participation of every students and able to express their opinion.

According to the results of the present study, it was found that effectiveness of the teaching can be assessed by active involvement of students as in integrated teaching and seminars. Khan T, Hassali M et al in their studies proved that active participation of the students is one of the important factor for effective learning during the class. [11]

Conclusion

The study concludes that, the students prefer different combination of teaching learning method like chalk and talk with PPT, CBL, seminars, ECE, SGD, demonstration etc for better understanding, higher order thinking and easy way of learning.

Therefore it is necessary to implement innovative skills through different teaching learning techniques on a daily basis especially for abstract sub-

jects like biochemistry instead of one or two traditional way of teaching, so that we can improve the overall learning of students in all aspects.

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